

Oxidation studies of formic and oxalic acids by morpholinium fluorochromate : Kinetic and mechanistic study

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Abstract : Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of formic and oxalic acids by morpholinium fluorochromate (MFC) have been studied in dimethylsulphoxide. The main product of oxidation is carbon dioxide. The reaction is first order with respect to MFC. Michaelis-Menten type of kinetics were observed with respect to the reductants. The reaction is acid-catalysed and the acid dependence has the form : $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b[\text{H}^+]$. The oxidation of α -deuterioformic acid exhibits a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}} = 5.30$ at 298 K). The reaction has been studied in nineteen different organic solvents and the solvent effect has been analysed using Taft's and Swain's multiparametric equations. The temperature dependence of the kinetic isotope effect indicates the presence of a symmetrical cyclic transition state in the rate-determining step. Suitable mechanisms have been proposed.

Keywords : Kinetics, mechanism, halochromate, organic acids, oxidation.

Introduction

Halochromates have been used as mild and selective oxidizing reagents in synthetic organic chemistry¹. Morpholinium fluorochromate (MFC) is also one of such compounds used for the oxidation of benzylic alcohols². We have been interested in the kinetic and mechanistic aspects of the oxidation by complexed Cr^{VI} species and several reports on halochromates have already reported from our laboratory³⁻⁷. There seems to be no report on the oxidation aspects of organic acids by morpholinium fluorochromate. Therefore, we report in this paper the kinetics of oxidation of oxalic and formic acids by MFC in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) as solvent. The mechanistic aspects are discussed. A suitable mechanism has also been proposed.

Results and discussion

Stoichiometry : The oxidation of organic acids leads to the formation of carbon dioxide. The stoichiometric determination indicated the following overall reactions :

MFC undergoes two-electron change. This is in accordance with the earlier observations with structurally similar other halochromates also. It has already been shown that both PFC⁸ and PCC⁹ act as two electron oxidants and are reduced to chromium(IV) species by determining the oxidation state of chromium by magnetic susceptibility, ESR and IR studies.

Rate laws : The reactions were found to be first order with respect to MFC. The reaction rate increases with an increase in [Organic acid] but not linearly (Table 1). The Fig. 1 depicts a typical kinetic run. A plot of $1/[\text{Organic acid}]$ versus $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ is linear with an intercept on the rate ordinate. Thus the reactions exhibited Michaelis-Menten type kinetics with respect to the organic acids. This indicates the following overall mechanism (3) and (4) and the rate law (5).

$$\text{Rate} = k_2 K [\text{MFC}] [\text{Organic acid}] / (1 + K [\text{Organic acid}]) \quad (5)$$

The dependence of the reaction rate on reductant concentration was studied at different temperatures and the

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of organic acids by MFC at 298 K

10 ³ [MFC] (mol dm ⁻³)	[Organic acid] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ⁴ k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)	
		Oxalic acid	Formic acid
1.00	0.10	34.8	4.88
1.00	0.20	43.4	7.29
1.00	0.40	49.5	9.68
1.00	0.60	51.9	10.9
1.00	0.80	53.2	11.6
1.00	1.00	54.1	12.1
1.00	1.50	55.2	12.7
1.00	3.00	56.4	13.5
2.00	0.40	51.3	9.36
4.00	0.40	48.6	8.82
6.00	0.40	50.4	9.54
8.00	0.40	48.0	8.73
1.00	0.20	44.1 ^a	7.11 ^a

^aContained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

Fig. 1. Oxidation of FA acid by MFC : A typical kinetic run.

values of K and k_2 were evaluated from the double reciprocal plots (Fig. 2). The thermodynamic and activation parameters, at 298 K, were also calculated from the values of K and k_2 respectively, at four different temperatures (Tables 2 and 3). Fig. 2 depicts a typical kinetic run.

Induced polymerization of acrylonitrile : The oxidation of organic acids by MFC, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, failed to induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile. Further, the addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on the rate (Table 1).

Effect of hydrogen ions : The reaction is catalysed by

Fig. 2. Oxidation of FA acid by MFC : A double reciprocal plot.

hydrogen ions. The hydrogen-ion dependence has the following form (Table 4). The values of a and b , for oxalic acid, are $3.25 \pm 0.31 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $12.5 \pm 0.51 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively ($r^2 = 0.9933$). The corresponding values for the oxidation of formic acid are $0.46 \pm 0.01 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $1.79 \pm 0.01 \times 10^{-3}$ ($r^2 = 0.9999$)

$$k_{\text{obs}} = a + b[\text{H}^+] \quad (6)$$

Kinetic isotope effect : To ascertain the importance of the cleavage of the $\alpha\text{-C-H}$ bond in the rate-determining step, the oxidation of DFA was studied. The results recorded in Tables 2 and 3, showed that while the formation constant, K , for the ordinary and deuteriated formic acids have almost identical values, the rate constant for the decomposition of the complex, k_2 , exhibited a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}} = 5.90$ at 298 K).

Reactive oxidizing species : The observed hydrogen-ion dependence suggests that the reaction follows two mechanistic pathways, one is acid-independent and the other is acid-dependent. The acid-catalysis may well be attributed to a protonation of MFC to yield a protonated Cr^{VI} species which is a stronger oxidant and electrophile (7).

Table 2. Dependence of the reaction rate on hydrogen-ion concentration

[MFC] = 0.001 mol dm ⁻³	[Acid] = 0.10 mol dm ⁻³					Temp. = 298 K
Acid	0.10	0.20	0.40	0.60	0.80	1.00
	(TsOH) (mol dm ⁻³)					
OA ($10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$) (s ⁻¹)	45.9	57.6	82.8	108	126	162
FA ($10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$) (s ⁻¹)	6.48	8.10	11.7	15.3	18.9	22.5

Table 3. Formation constants and thermodynamic parameters for the organic acid-MFC complexes

Acid	K (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				$-\Delta H^*$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta S^*$ (J mol ¹ K ⁻¹)	$-\Delta G^*$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K			
OA	31.5	15.3	7.04	3.51	58.5±0.8	166±2	9.16±0.6
FA	6.12	5.13	4.23	3.33	17.8±0.7	38±2	6.50±0.6
DFA	6.57	5.58	4.68	3.78	16.4±0.6	33±2	6.72±0.5

Table 4. Rate constants and activation parameters for the organic acid-MFC complexes

Acid	$10^4 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta S^*$ (J mol ¹ K ⁻¹)	ΔG^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K			
OA	27.9	57.6	117	243	52.3±0.8	113±3	85.7±0.7
FA	7.38	14.4	28.0	55.8	48.7±0.7	136±3	89.2±0.7
DFA	1.21	2.46	5.16	10.5	52.4±0.8	138±3	93.5±0.6
k_H/k_D	6.10	5.85	5.58	5.31			

Formation of a protonated Cr^{VI} species has earlier been postulated in the reactions of structurally similar halochromates.

Solvent effect : The oxidation of formic acid was studied in 19 different organic solvents. The choice of solvents was limited due to the solubility of MFC and its reaction with primary and secondary alcohols. There was no reaction with the solvents chosen. The kinetics were similar in all the solvents. The values of K and k_2 are recorded in Table 5. The formation constant of the intermediate complex, K , did not vary much with the solvent but the rate constant, k_2 , exhibited much variation in values with different solvents.

The rate constants, k_2 , in 18 solvents (CS₂ was not

considered, as the complete range of solvent parameters was not available) were correlated in terms of the linear solvation energy relationship (8) of Kamlet *et al.*¹⁰.

$$\log k_2 = A_0 + p\pi^* + b\beta + a\alpha \quad (8)$$

In this equation, π^* represents the solvent polarity, α is the hydrogen bond acceptor basicities and β is the hydrogen bond donor acidity. A_0 is the intercept term. It may be mentioned here that out of the 18 solvents, 12 have a value of zero for α . The results of correlation analyses in terms of eq. (8), a biparametric equation involving π^* and β , and separately with π^* and β are given below as eqs. (9)–(12).

$$\log k_2 = -4.03 + 1.95 (\pm 0.21)\pi^* + 0.18 (\pm 0.18)\beta + 0.28 (0.17)\alpha \quad (9)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8731; sd = 0.20; n = 18; \psi = 0.39$$

$$\log k_2 = -3.96 + 1.84 (\pm 0.22)\pi^* + 0.27 (\pm 0.18)\beta \quad (10)$$

Table 5. Effect of solvents on the oxidation of formic acid by MFC at 298 K

Solvents	K (dm ⁻³ mol ⁻¹)	$10^5 k_2$ (s ⁻¹)	Solvents	K (dm ⁻³ mol ⁻¹)	$10^5 k_2$ (s ⁻¹)
Chloroform	5.88	49.0	Toluene	5.72	7.94
1,2-Dichloroethane	4.65	41.7	Acetophenone	5.54	54.9
Dichloromethane	5.22	44.7	THF	6.15	14.8
DMSO	5.13	144	t-Butylalcohol	5.36	20.9
Acetone	5.63	33.9	1,4-Dioxane	4.44	17.8
DMF	6.12	63.1	1,2-Dimethoxyethane	4.47	9.55
Butanone	5.55	27.5	CS ₂	4.77	3.47
Nitrobenzene	4.99	51.3	Acetic acid	5.80	15.8
Benzene	5.18	10.5	Ethyl acetate	5.82	12.3
Cyclohexane	6.00	0.69			

$$R^2 = 0.8474; sd = 0.21; n = 18; \psi = 0.41$$

$$\log k_2 = -3.91 + 1.91 (\pm 0.22)\pi^* \quad (11)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8239; sd = 0.22; n = 18; \psi = 0.43$$

$$\log k_2 = -2.89 + 0.60 (\pm 0.41)\beta \quad (12)$$

$$r^2 = 0.1210; sd = 0.49; n = 18; \psi = 0.96$$

Here n is the number of data points and ψ is the Exner's statistical parameter¹¹.

Kamlet's¹⁰ triparametric equation explains *ca.* 87% of the effect of solvent on the oxidation. However, by Exner's¹³ criterion the correlation is not even satisfactory [*cf.* eq. (9)]. The major contribution is of solvent polarity. It alone accounts for 85% of the data. Both β and α play relatively minor roles.

The data on solvent effect were also analyzed in terms of Swain's equation¹² of cation- and anion-solvating concept of the solvents also (13).

$$\log k_2 = aA + bB + C \quad (13)$$

Here A represents the anion-solvating power of the solvent and B the cation-solvating power. C is the intercept term. ($A + B$) is postulated to represent the solvent polarity. The rates in different solvents were analysed in terms of eq. (13), separately with A and B and with ($A + B$).

$$\log k_2 = 1.36 (\pm 0.04)A + 1.85 (\pm 0.03)B - 3.72 \quad (14)$$

$$R_2 = 0.9962; sd = 0.03; n = 19; \psi = 0.07$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.09 (\pm 0.61)A - 2.85 \quad (15)$$

$$r^2 = 0.1587; sd = 0.49; n = 19; \psi = 0.94$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.75 (\pm 0.24)B - 4.17 \quad (16)$$

$$r^2 = 0.7546; sd = 0.27; n = 19; \psi = 0.51$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.69 (\pm 0.07)(A + B) - 3.74 \quad (17)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9731; sd = 0.09; n = 19; \psi = 0.17$$

The rates of decomposition of the complex in different solvents showed an excellent correlation in Swain's equation [*cf.* eq.(14)] with the cation-solvating power playing the major role. In fact, the cation-solvation alone account for *ca.* 75% of the data. The correlation with the anion-solvating power was very poor. The solvent polarity, represented by ($A + B$), also accounted for *ca.* 97% of the data. In view of the fact that solvent polarity is able to account for *ca.* 98% of the data, an attempt was made to correlate the rate with the relative permittivity of the solvent. However, a plot of log (rate) against the inverse of the relative permittivity is not linear ($r^2 = 0.4742$; sd

$$= 0.39; \psi = 0.74).$$

Mechanism

The presence of a substantial kinetic isotopic effect confirmed that an α -C-H bond is cleaved in the rate-determining step. The observed kinetics indicate the formation of an intermediate complex in a rapid pre-equilibrium. However, the highly unfavourable entropy term obtained in the complex formation of oxalic acid-MFC reaction suggests that oxalic acid acts as a bidentate ligand and forms a cyclic intermediate complex. In the chromic acid oxidation also, the formation of a cyclic anhydride intermediate, oxalyl chromate, has been postulated¹³. The value of formation constant, $9.5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, reported by Hassan and Rocek¹³ compares favorably with the values obtained in this investigation. The absence of any effect of a radical scavenger, acrylonitrile, indicates that a hydrogen abstraction mechanism, giving rise to free radicals, is unlikely.

For the formic acid oxidation, the cation-solvating power of the solvents plays a relatively more important role. Therefore, formation of an electron-deficient carbon centre in the transition state is indicated. Thus the decomposition of MFC-formic acid complex may involve a hydride ion transfer via an anhydride intermediate (Scheme 1).

This hydride ion transfer may take place either via an anhydride or by an acyclic process. The involvement of a concerted cyclic process is supported by a study of the temperature dependence of the kinetic isotope effect¹⁴. The data for protio- and deuterio-formic acids when fitted in the familiar expression $k_H/k_D = A_H/A_D \exp(-\Delta H^*/RT)$ show a direct correspondence with the properties of a symmetrically transition state in which the differences in the activation energies for the protio and deuterio compounds are equal to the differences in the zero point energies of the corresponding C-H and C-D bonds (*ca.* 4.5 kJ mol^{-1}) and the entropies of the activation of the respective reactions are almost equal^{15,16}. Bordwell¹⁷ has documented a very cogent evidence against the occurrence of concerted one-step bimolecular processes by hydrogen transfer and it is evident that in the present studies also the hydrogen transfer does not occur by an acyclic biomolecular process. It is well established that intrinsically concerted sigmatropic reactions, characterised by transfer of hydrogen in a cyclic transition state, are the only truly symmetrical processes involving a linear hydrogen transfer¹⁸. Littler¹⁹ has also shown that a cyclic

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

hydride transfer, in the oxidation of alcohols by Cr^{VI}, involves six electrons and, being a Hückel-type system, is an allowed process. Thus, a transition state having a planar, cyclic and symmetrical structure can be envisaged for the decomposition of the ester intermediate. Hence, the overall mechanism is proposed to involve the formation of a chromate ester in a fast pre-equilibrium step and then a decomposition of the ester in a subsequent slow step via a cyclic concerted symmetrical transition state leading to the product (Schemes 1 and 2).

The observed dependence on the hydrogen-ion concentration in both the reactions shows there to be an additional acid-catalysed pathway. This may be attributed to a rapid reversible protonation of the anhydride, with the protonated anhydride decomposing at a rate higher than the decomposition of the unprotonated anhydride (Scheme 2).

Experimental

Materials : MFC and α -deuterioformic acid (DCO₂H or DFA) were prepared by the reported methods^{2,20}. Due to the non-aqueous nature of the medium, toluene-*p*-sulphonic acid (TsOH) was used as a source of hydrogen ions. TsOH is a strong acid and in a polar solvent like DMSO it is likely to be completely ionised. Solvents were purified by the usual methods²¹.

Stoichiometry : To determine the stoichiometry, an excess of TPSD ($\times 5$ or greater) was reacted with the organic acid in DMSO (100 cm³) and the amount of residual TPSD after the completion of reaction was measured spectrophotometrically at 365 nm. No quantitative determination of carbon dioxide formed was carried out.

Kinetic measurements : The reactions were followed under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping a large excess ($\times 15$ or greater) of the organic acid over TPSD. The temperature was kept constant to ± 0.1 °C. The solvent was DMSO, unless specified otherwise. The reactions were followed by monitoring the decrease in the concentration of TPSD spectrophotometrically at 365 nm for up to 80% of the reaction. No other reactant or product has any significant absorption at this wavelength. The pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{obs} , were evaluated from the linear ($r = 0.995\text{--}0.999$) plots of $\log [\text{TPSD}]$ against time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$.

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References

1. E. J. Corey and W. J. Suggs, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1975, 2647; F. S. Guziec and F. A. Luzio, *Synthesis*, 1980, 691; M. N. Bhattacharjee, M. K. Choudhuri, H. S. Dasgupta, N. Roy and D. T. Khathing, *Synthesis*, 1982, 588; K. Balasubramanian and V. Prathiba, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1986, **25B**, 326.
2. S. Z. S. Alangi, H. S. Ghotbabadi, M. T. Baei and S. Naderi, *Hindawi E-J. Chem.*, 2011, **8**, 815.
3. D. Sharma, P. Panchariya, K. Vadera and P. K. Sharma, *J. Sulfur Chem.*, 2011, **32**, 315.
4. D. Sharma, P. Panchariya, P. Purohit and P. K. Sharma, *Oxid. Commun.*, 2012, **35**, 821.
5. T. Purohit, M. Patel, O. Praksh and P. K. Sharma, *Int. J. Chem.*, 2013, **2**, 436.
6. L. Mathur, A. Choudhary, Om Prakash and Pradeep K. Sharma, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2014, **26**, 2597.
7. U. Soni, D. Yajurvedi, S. Vyas, O. Prakash and P. K. Sharma, *Eur. Chem. Bull.*, 2015, **4**, 449.
8. H. C. Brown, G. C. Rao and S. U. Kulkarni, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1979, **44**, 2809.
9. M. N. Bhattacharjee, M. K. Choudhuri and S. Purakayastha, *Tetrahedron*, 1987, **43**, 5389.
10. M. J. Kamlet, J. L. M. Abboud, M. H. Abraham and R. W. Taft, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1983, **48**, 2877 and references cited therein.
11. O. Exner, *Collect. Chem. Czech. Commun.*, 1966, **31**, 3222.
12. C. G. Swain, M. S. Swain, A. L. Powel and S. Alunni, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **105**, 502.
13. F. Hassan and J. Rocek, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **92**, 9073.
14. H. Kwart and J. H. Nickel, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **95**, 3394.
15. H. Kwart and M. C. Latimer, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **93**, 3770.
16. H. Kwart and J. Slutsky, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1972, 1182.
17. F. G. Bordwell, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1974, **5**, 374.
18. R. W. Woodward and R. Hoffmann, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Eng.*, 1969, **8**, 781.
19. J. S. Littler, *Tetrahedron*, 1971, **27**, 81.
20. K. B. Wiberg and R. Stewart, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 1214.
21. D. D. Perrin, L. Armarego and D. R. Perrin, "Purification of Organic Compounds", Pergamon, Oxford, 1966.